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**Soft Modelling of the Photovoltaic Modules
based on MATLAB/Simulink**

**(基于 MATLAB/Simulink 光伏模块的
软件建模)**

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ABSTRACT

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The world's electric power generation is gradually shifting ground from conventional to renewable energy sources (RES) in order to mitigate the negative consequences of the former. Solar photovoltaic energy is regarded as the most attractive of all the RES due to its low installation and maintenance costs, longer lifetime and shorter payback period. A significant increase in the number of installed solar photovoltaics was recorded over the past decade, leading to a substantial decrease in panels cost by about 80%. Notwithstanding, the low power conversion efficiency is one of the notable setbacks facing the solar photovoltaic system (SPS). Therefore, an accurate, robust, and flexible modelling and simulation of the PV modules are necessary for an improvement in maximum power extraction, partial shading condition (PSC) elimination, accurate and reliable photovoltaic (PV) panel sizing, design of power converters during the development of stand-alone or integrated SPS with the micro-grid or hybrid DC/AC grid systems amongst others.

Based on these, the present study used MATLAB programming to implement the five-parameter single-diode model (SDM) PV modules in the MATLAB/Simulink using the manufacturer's datasheet information. MATLAB_R2020a version was used for the implementation. The modules were implemented through the I-V equation parameters estimation of the SDM from the manufacturer's datasheet. The performance of different PV module technologies implemented was evaluated at STC. Analyses of the I-V and P-V curves characteristics of the developed models were carried out. Further analyses of the implemented models were conducted under various test conditions. Models validation was performed by comparing the results obtained with that of selected in-built PV models. Different factors affecting the modules' performance were also evaluated. Finally, a Simulink model of the PV module was also developed for easy to use with any circuit simulator.

The proposed modelling technique meets the key features of minimal differences between the modelled and actual measurements data, most especially at the maximum power points, while exhibiting a fast convergence with good precision. It also proved to have improved the results obtained in previous studies, which employed similar approaches but with many initial guess values.

Keywords – Single-diode PV model, 5-parameter model, PV module, Double-diode PV model, MATLAB programming.

DECLARATION

I hereby certify that this dissertation constitutes my own product, that where the language of others is set forth, quotation marks so indicate, and that appropriate credit is given where I have used the language, ideas, expressions or writings of another.

I declare that the dissertation describes original work that has not previously been presented for the award of any other degree of any institution.

Signed,

Shuaibu Musa Adam

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
MPPT	Maximum power point tracking
SDM	Single-diode model
RES	Renewable energy sources
WOA	Whale Optimization Algorithm
SPS	Solar photovoltaic system
STC	Standard test condition
WEC	World Energy Council
GUI	Graphical user interface
COA	Coyote Optimization Algorithm
P-V	Power-voltage
DC	Direct current
WEF	World Energy Forum
MPP	Maximum power point
CIS	Copper Indium Diselenide
DDM	Double-diode model
PV	Photovoltaic
PSC	Partial shading condition
I-V	Current-voltage
DE	Differential evolution
RMSE	Root Mean Square Error
UN	United Nations
AC	Alternating current
P&O	Perturb and observe

LIST OF SYMBOLS

Symbol	Definition	Unit
m	Diode ideality factor	-
I_{sat}	Reverse-saturation current	ampere (A)
I_L	Light-generated current	ampere (A)
V_{mp}	Voltage at MPP	volt (V)
R_s	Series resistance	ohm (Ω)
q	Charge of an electron	-
V_{oc}	Open-circuit voltage	volt (V)
V_{gap}	Bandgap energy	-
I_{rr}	Solar irradiance	watts/sq.metre (W/m^2)
K_i	Temperature coefficient of I_{sc}	A/ $^{\circ}C$
I_{mp}	Current at MPP	ampere (A)
V_t	Thermal voltage	volt (V)
P_{max}	Maximum power	watts (W)
V	Cell voltage	volt (V)
T	Temperature	Kelvin (K)
N_p	Parallel-connected cells	-
K_v	Temperature coefficient of V_{oc}	V/ $^{\circ}C$
R_{sh}	Shunt resistance	ohm (Ω)
N_s	Series-connected cells	-
k	Boltzmann's constant	-
I_{sc}	Short-circuit current	ampere (A)

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Chapter 1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Introduction

Excessive burning of fossil fuels for electric power generation over the past centuries has continued to affect present-day lives adversely. For almost two to three decades now, mitigating the climate change issues accumulated over time has been one of the major concerns of the United Nations (UN) [1]. This is because of its negative consequences that are being witnessed in almost all sectors of human existence. Therefore, the threats posed by burning fossils on lives and properties can never be overemphasised.

Similarly, according to the World Energy Forum (WEF) report, the coal, natural gas, and fossils reserves are predicted to be exhausted within the next ten (10) decades [2]. At the same time, the global electricity demand peak will be reached by the year 2030, as contained in the World Energy Council (WEC) report [3]. As such, finding alternate energy sources that will replace the conventional ones while mitigating their negative consequences are the current challenges facing the entire world. Policymakers and energy planners believed that renewable energy sources would be the lasting and feasible solutions to the lingering world's energy crises because of their regenerative, cleanliness and environmentally friendly nature [4, 5]. Many ground-breaking breakthroughs and cutting-edge research on renewable energy sources (RES) have continued to be explored since around the 70s [6] with the common goals of addressing the challenges mentioned earlier.

Solar photovoltaic energy is regarded as the most attractive of all the RES for electric power generation due to its low installation and maintenance costs, longer lifetime and shorter payback period [5, 7-9]. It can also be designed to suit any kind of power requirements (i.e. variable system size ranging from very small to the largest); noise-free power generation as no moving parts are required. These are some of its further advantages in comparison to other renewables. There is a significant increase in the number of installed solar photovoltaics over

the past decade, which resulted in the decrease of the panels cost by about 80%, thereby making the technology more viable for commercial applications [10]. This is aided by continuous improvement in the efficiency of solar conversion materials and other solar photovoltaic systems (SPS) components.

In photovoltaic (PV) power generation, direct current (DC) electricity is produced when photons illuminate semiconductor materials [6] via the process known as the photovoltaic effect [2]. The generated power can be used directly, stored, or converted to another form for long-distance transmission. However, the low power conversion efficiency of the PV panels is one of the significant setbacks facing the SPS [11]. According to many studies, it was estimated that only 10-20% of the total insolation falling on the solar panels is converted into useful energy [7]. A more significant portion of the falling irradiance is reflected in the atmosphere or converted to heat energy, which further deteriorates the panel's performance. In some instances, a lower range of efficiency may be recorded due to variations in irradiation, the load types and the panel temperature, respectively.

Therefore, for large power applications, there is a need to join multiple PV arrays, which invariably adds cost to the overall system. To extract maximum power output while maintaining a smaller PV array size and minimising the overall system cost, constant peak power operating conditions of the panels must be ensured [9, 11]. This is to say, conditions like impedance matching of the internal resistance with the voltage source have to be provided for optimum power delivery. For this to be realised, additional components like maximum power point (MPP) tracker, partial shading condition (PSC) eliminators and so on are required. The tracker assists modules and other power converters in extracting maximum power from the insolation in addition to the operating conditions and other physical constraints. It should be borne in mind that all these additional components require the operation of *accurately modelled PV modules* to achieve any desired level of power output.

Furthermore, for accurate and reliable panel sizing, PV system specification, design of power converters during the development of stand-alone or integrated SPS with the micro-grid or hybrid DC/AC grid systems; there is a need for the same *robust and flexible modelling and simulation* of the PV modules in software like MATLAB/Simulink, PSIM, PSpice etc. [10]. As such, numerous computer modelling and simulation programs are being developed to ensure the optimum design of the SPS before the installation processes [8]. Meanwhile, the accuracy and reliability of the developed programs solely depend on the types of PV cell models used.

Renewable energy engineers, energy designers as well as research and development scientists are continuously carrying out large volumes of researches on finding novel approaches to the modelling of PV modules which are applicable to all kind of SPS; thereby enabling constant maximum power operation for maximum power output delivery from the panel [10].

1.2 Solar Photovoltaic Modules

The PV cells/modules' performance determinants primarily depend on the values of temperature, irradiance and load current [12]. The effects of junction-diode, series (R_s) and shunt (R_{sh}) resistances also play vital roles in the power output and I-V characteristics of the cell/module. For an in-depth investigation into their efficiencies, additional parameters like the fill factor are also taken into consideration.

The smallest unit of a PV module is known as the solar cell. Irradiating the solar cell causes valance band excitation of the electron when the energy of the photon exceeds the bandgap energy (V_{gap}) of the semiconductor material [13]. This leads to the creation of a hole by the electron. Therefore, the n-type region accumulates electron while the p-type region gets holes as a result of the depletion layer, which subsequently produces a voltage. Upon connecting to the external circuit, a light-generated current (I_L) is produced [12, 13]. The photo-generation process of a PV cell [12] is shown in figure 1.

Fig. 1: The process of voltage and photo-current generation

1.2.1 Mathematical model of a PV cell

The accuracy of PV modules modelling and simulation depends on the type of PV cell model used [14]. An ideal PV cell is simply a current source with a p-n junction diode connected in parallel [12, 13]. In contrast, a practical PV cell consists of the shunt (R_{sh}) and series (R_s) resistances in addition. These two resistances determine the external behaviour of the model. There is a large number of literature on PV module modelling techniques, which are accompanied by lots of trade-offs between complexity and accuracy [15]. The most commonly used model consists of only one current source, a p-n junction diode, series and shunt resistances, respectively [10, 12, 14]. It also forms the basis for all other models. Figure 2 shows the equivalent circuit models for both the ideal and practical PV devices [16].

Fig. 2: PV cell equivalent-circuit model

From the basic theory of semiconductors, the net current of an ideal PV cell, which describes its I-V characteristics, is governed by the equation [17, 18]:

$$I = I_L - I_D \quad (1)$$

Where:

I = net current of the PV cell; I_L = light – generated current;

I_D = Shockley – diode equation

$$I = I_L - I_{sat} \left[e^{\left(\frac{qV_d}{m \cdot kT}\right)} - 1 \right] \quad (2)$$

Where:

I_{sat} = reverse – saturation current; q = charge of an electron; m = diode ideality factor;

V_d = p – n junction diode voltage; k = Boltzmann’s constant ;

T = temperature of the p – n junction

The performance analyses of this type of cell are done by plotting the I-V and P-V curves. As previously highlighted, the output current of the PV cell depends on the values of irradiation, temperature, reverse-saturation current, shunt resistance, series resistance, short circuit current and open-circuit voltage, respectively.

1.2.2 PV module and array

For large power generation, a single PV cell is insufficient. Therefore, a PV module or array is needed, depending on the purpose and power requirements. For this to be achieved, numerous solar cells are connected in different combinations. A module is formed when cells are connected in series and parallel arrangements, whereas electrically connecting modules in series-parallel combination form an array [7, 12, 14, 17, 19]. Figure 3 shows the PV cell, module and array [7].

The ideal PV cell equation (1) is not adequate to determine the module’s I-V characteristics for a practical PV device. Thus, by providing some additional parameters to the basic equation, the I-V characteristics of the module can be obtained as follows [17]:

$$I = I_L - I_{sat} \left[e^{\left(\frac{V + IR_s}{m \cdot V_t}\right)} - 1 \right] - \frac{(V + IR_s)}{R_{sh}} \quad (3)$$

In which:

$V_t = \frac{N_s k T}{q}$ = thermal voltage of the module and N_s = number of series – connected cells

R_{sh} = equivalent shunt resistance; R_s = equivalent series resistance; V = cell voltage

While all other parameters have their usual meaning.

Fig. 3: PV cell, module and array

The effects of parallel and series cells combination of modules are better expressed by modifying equation (3) into [20]:

$$I = I_L \cdot N_p - I_{sat} \cdot N_p \left[e^{\left(\frac{V + IR_s}{mV_t} \right)} - 1 \right] - \frac{(V \cdot N_p + IR_s \cdot N_p)}{R_{sh} \cdot N_p} \quad (4)$$

In which N_p represents the number of connected cells in parallel.

From equation (3), three distinctive points of interest on the I-V curve characteristics can be obtained. These are: the open-circuit voltage point, short-circuit current point and the MPP, respectively. These are shown in figure 4 [21].

1.3 Problem Statement

Large volumes of PV panel modelling techniques are available in the literature. However, most of the techniques use an arbitrary value of the *diode ideality constant* (m) [22], which consequently affects the accuracy of the other module parameters estimation. The effect is more prominent in methods that employ *iterative techniques* (due to sensitivity of the initial guess values) [23] in determining these unknown parameters, leading to *convergence* problems.

The ideality factor basically refers to the representation of the extent to which the p-n junction diode of a PV device behaves in reality and how it is related to the ideal I-V Schocklye-diode equation. However, the ideality is found not to be ideal as a result of some second-order issues [22]. Because the parameter affects the performance and shape of the modules' characteristics curves, significant attention has been given to its accurate determination.

Fig. 4: Practical PV device I-V curve characteristics at STC

Similarly, in some approaches, the R_{sh} is assumed to be very high or infinite and hence neglected [13]. Meanwhile, this type of assumption leads to a large error in the algorithm implementation, especially at very high temperature and irradiance conditions.

Therefore, the current study focused on using MATLAB programming to model and simulate PV modules in MATLAB/Simulink environment, leading to flexible, more robust, and simpler PV modules that fit into many SPS design requirements. The proposed algorithm used the manufacturer's datasheet information to implement a five-parameter single-diode model (SDM) PV module.

1.4 Research Scope and Objectives

A step-by-step implementation procedure for PV panels modelling in MATLAB/Simulink environment has been presented in this research. In the process, the following were also be achieved:

1. Derivation and solution of practical PV device equivalent-circuit parameters for SDM of the selected panels at STC using the manufacturer's datasheet information.
2. The I-V and P-V curves characteristics results of the tested panels were also compared based on the manufacturer's datasheet values to verify their agreement over a range of insolation and temperature values.
3. Finally, the effects of changes in the diode ideality constant for the different modules were evaluated.

1.5 Approach

MATLAB programming was used to implement the five-parameter SDM PV module in the MATLAB editor window and the Simulink environment. The performance of the implemented modules/array were evaluated at STC. Further analyses of the proposed modules were conducted by varying the operating temperature and solar irradiance. Analyses of the I-V and P-V curves characteristics of the developed models were carried out. Models validation was performed by comparing the results obtained with that of the selected in-built PV model using the manufacturer's datasheet. During the model validation, different factors affecting the performance of the module are evaluated. Finally, the PV module's Simulink model was also developed and tested for use with other SPS components like converter, MPPT algorithms, battery load, etc.

1.6 Chapters Arrangement

The subsequent chapters of this research report have been organised in the following arrangement. In chapter 2, a background of the study and a review of related literature were presented. The research methodology was outlined in chapter 3, while research findings, analyses and discussions were presented in chapter 4. The conclusion of the study was contained in chapter 5. The report ended by offering the list of bibliography and appendices accordingly.

Chapter 2. BACKGROUND AND REVIEW OF LITERATURE

2.1 Introduction

Over the past few decades, many different approaches of modelling techniques on how to accurately model and simulate PV modules are being designed, implemented and published. In this section, the SDM PV module is first discussed, followed by a review of the double-diode model (DDM). Subsequently, complex models comprising of more than two-diodes and other additional components are presented. Finally, a short conclusion based on the reviewed literature is presented.

2.2 Single-diode PV Model

A SDM consisting of one series and parallel resistances was chosen as the PV cell model [12] and subsequently applied for the module/array modelling. The modelling and simulation were carried out in the MATLAB/Simulink environment. Factors affecting the output performance of SPS (i.e. bypass-diode, temperature, shading and irradiance) were analysed. It was found out that the behaviour of PV cell, module and array can be predicted using the developed model under varying environmental conditions and physical constraints. In addition, a commercial-scale PV power system was also simulated using the proposed model. The proposed technique has proved to possess some characteristics useful in developing a control system for the PV system under maximum power operating conditions. However, the major drawback of the proposed method is the use of constant value for the diode ideality, which affected its accuracy.

A similar study used the Differential Evolution (DE) algorithm to improve the computational technique for estimating the SDM parameters [8]. The values of R_{sh} , R_s , m , I_{sat} and I_L of the selected modules were analysed under different environmental conditions. The computational burden of estimating the parameters was further simplified using the DE algorithm to find only the (R_s) and (m) values. In contrast, the remaining parameters were analytically solved using these known values. The convergence speed of the computation was also increased. Better

output results were obtained, especially under low levels of irradiance. Despite the improvement recorded, the proposed technique may not be convenient to use in most SPS design as it involved advanced and complex computation while at the same time requiring longer execution speed.

In a research titled “Comparative study of MATLAB-simulated and conventional Si-based solar panel,” a SDM PV cell was used for the simulation; meanwhile, a Silicon-based solar panel was chosen for the experimental analysis [14]. ET 250 photovoltaic trainer was used for this analysis. Maths block functions were used to build a generalised PV module for the simulation in the Simulink environment. The model was then analysed under different environmental and physical conditions. Various series combinations of modules were made to verify further the corresponding parameters change in both set-ups. The results obtained in both systems are in good agreement. Thus, suitable for application in SPS. However, both systems used arbitrary constant values of some module parameters; thus, an improvement can be observed if those assumptions are eliminated in future studies.

A new modelling and simulation method for PV modules using SDM was proposed. The study focuses on finding the module parameters by adjusting the I-V curve equation at three important points [17]. These are the short-circuit, open-circuit and maximum power points, in which the manufacturer’s datasheet information are used for the modelling process. In this technique, only the diode ideality factor (m) was assumed to be constant. Good agreement between the I-V & P-V curves for both the experimental and modelled data were obtained. The proposed algorithm also considered the effects of series and parallel resistances, respectively. Thus, following the adjusted equations, a PV circuit model was built using simple math blocks and can be used with most circuit simulators. Models validation were performed by varying the operating conditions and the results obtained are in good agreement.

Further study on enhancement of the photovoltaic panel for maximum power operation was conducted [24]. MATLAB/Simulink software was used for model development and simulation.

The proposed model is basically a practical single-diode PV device with an added capacitor across its p-n junction for precision improvement during static, dynamic and transient processes. The presence of a significant voltage change coefficient and SimPowerSystems blocks in the proposed model further differentiate it from the Simscape library model. Parameters estimation and comparison of the proposed model with that of the MATLAB 2009 Simscape library are done. Models validation was carried out using the experimental data obtained from a real photovoltaic panel. The results obtained from the proposed model analyses are closer to that of the actual panel than the Simscape library model results. All the simulations were performed under steady-state conditions. As such, the nature of their agreement under dynamic states has not been covered by the study. Meanwhile, an assumed constant value of the ideality factor was used. The R_s and R_{sh} were considered independent parameters, thus computed differently, all of which affect the proposed technique's accuracy.

A study on the modelling and simulation of PV cells in the MATLAB/Simulink environment was performed using a SDM PV cell. MPP variations of the developed model under different temperature and irradiance levels were also investigated [25]. Validation of the proposed model was performed using the real environmental conditions of the Sultanate of Oman. The I-V & P-V curves characteristics of both the simulated and experimental models are in good agreement. However, the parameter extraction method used in the model was not straightforward.

For simulation purposes and on-line applications in the PV system, the PV cell parameters need to be defined in every operation instance. However, this is not the case in most of the operating conditions. Therefore, the single-diode PV cell model was used to propose a new modelling technique to determine those required parameters using a fuzzy regression model [26]. The manufacturer's data sheet was used in defining the cell's parameters under a given set of operating conditions. Real output data obtained from a selected site was used in validating

the proposed model. However, the study is limited to only a narrow range of operating conditions. Thus, the model performance at all operating conditions has not been ascertained. Though, the results obtained are as good as the ones obtained using the analytical technique with some further advantages of determining the cell parameters without running the spice software.

Furthermore, new PV array modelling and MSX 64W PV simulation using maths block in MATLAB/Simulink environment was proposed. A Single-diode PV cell model was used for the PV array modelling with tags [27]. PV array characteristics were obtained by varying some of the physical and environmental parameters. Partial shading conditions under different scenarios were also analysed in the study. Good I-V and P-V curves characteristics that match the manufacturer's datasheet information were found. The proposed technique also presents a reliable and straightforward way of integrating the PV array with other hybrid system components at varying environmental conditions. Notwithstanding, some constant values of the I-V equation parameters were assumed; thus, the technique needs to be improved.

PV module characteristics were studied using MATLAB-Graphical User Interface (GUI) to analyse the effects of different conditions of temperature and irradiance on the modules' performance [28]. Single-diode equivalent circuit model was used for the study. Three models were used; two are based on the theoretical data, whereas the other is based on the experimental data. It was found out that, when precise values of temperature and irradiance of the array are known, the GUI model can be used to design systems that can work at MPP as well as monitoring the output parameters, irrespective of changes in the conditions.

Another study used a Lorentz LA30-12S photovoltaic panel while uses PV monocrystalline panel in MATLAB/Simulink environment to modelled and simulate the panels [2]. PV array characteristics were obtained by focusing on changes in some of the environmental conditions. Good I-V and P-V curves characteristics that match the manufacturer's datasheet information are found. The proposed methods are attractive because of simplicity in their implementation, as there are no technical difficulties in reproducing similar model using different input data.

A single-diode PV cell model was used to simulate the characteristics performance of solar modules in the MATLAB environment by Genetic coding process [29]. I-V and P-V characteristics of the module were obtained under different conditions of temperature and irradiance. STC and experimental data were used to validate the proposed method. The results obtained are in good agreement with the manufacturer's data and lies within the allowable tolerance range. The effect of input factors on the modules can be determined using the proposed method, unlike the experimental approach, in which the effects are difficult to be observed.

Finally, the visually programming of the single-diode PV cell model was performed in MATLAB/Simulink environment. Two PV modules were developed and analysed using the Simulink model and MATLAB mfile model, respectively [30]. Changes in solar irradiance and temperature were used as the basis for the module's analyses. Other changes in environmental and physical module conditions are also taken into consideration. The manufacturer's datasheet parameters of the Luxen LNSE-245p PV module were used for the simulation. The model is found to be suitable for solar cell simulations in hybrid systems.

2.3 Double-diode PV Model

Comparative performance of both single- and double-diode PV cell models using real weather data of Maiduguri, Nigeria, was performed [18]. MATLAB-Simscape library was used for the analyses. The I-V and P-V characteristics curves output for both models are found to be accurate and in agreement with the results obtained from the manufacturer's datasheet at STC. However, the double-diode model yields better results than the single-diode model. Overall, both models' performance increases with an increase in solar irradiance and vice versa.

A solar cell block of MATLAB/Simulink was used in building system block for the modelling and simulation of AMERESCO solar panel [31]. Double-diode equivalent circuit model (5-parameter model) was used for the module design. The manufacturer's datasheet information was used for the parameter's extraction. The accurate module parameters are obtained from the model, which agrees with the experimental results. The model's interface is found to be user-

friendly for students and renewable energy engineers to conduct similar simulations using different data. The developed model was validated by comparing the simulated results with that of the experimental approach. Future work is recommended to focus on the experimental extraction of I-V and P-V characteristics for a single PV module. Further modifications to the developed model could be made for an accurate response to the PSC.

DDM PV module was simulated and validated experimentally. SUNSET PX1506 panel was used for the experimental laboratory validation of the models at STC and under different environmental conditions [32]. The experimental I-V and P-V curve analyses were done using Software Top View 2006 and HT I-V 400 full PV systems analyser, respectively. Past convergence of PV module parameters was observed from the developed model. SDM was also analysed compared with the two-diode model. It was concluded that the proposed model provides simple, reliable, fast and accurate modelling of the two-diode PV module in the MATLAB/Simulink environment. Meanwhile, the two-diode model accuracy is found to be better than that of the single-diode model.

Accurate parameters computation method for the two-diode model of Copper Indium Diselenide (CIS) thin-film PV module was proposed using the DE technique [33]. In this method, simultaneous solutions of all module parameters are obtained and used for the modelling accordingly without keeping any of them constant, unlike in the conventional techniques. Two CIS thin-film modules experimental data are used to validate the developed method. Further comparison with already obtained results from the literature was made. In all, the proposed method is found to be excellent, particularly at high temperatures and low levels of irradiance.

Comparative performance analyses of different PV cell models were conducted in MATLAB/Simulink environment under normal and PSC [34]. Comparison of the ideal and general (single-diode with R_s , single-diode with R_s & R_{sh} , double-diode with R_s & R_{sh}) models were performed. The current, voltage and output power from the models are the key parameters compared through their I-V and P-V characteristic curves. Of all the results obtained, double-

diode with R_s & R_{sh} model exhibited accuracy closer to the real solar panel. However, its complexity in finding PV parameters is higher than that of other models. While results of single-diode with R_s and single-diode with R_s & R_{sh} are closer.

A complete SPS was researched to analyse the impacts of variation of environmental conditions on its performance, to propose an ideal solution for maximum power delivery from the system [35]. The off-grid system was designed, modelled and simulated in MATLAB/Simulink. The model was scrutinised using the environmental conditions of Bangladesh. A Double-diode PV cell model was used in the design of the system's PV modules. From the PV characteristics results obtained, the module was able to deliver the maximum power required to the load and is closer to the expected real datasheet values.

A diagram of the simplified two-diode equivalent circuit model described by [36] is shown in figure 5.

Fig. 5: Double-diode equivalent-circuit model

2.4 Other PV Models

An investigation into the non-linear diode equation has been carried out to find a solution to the PV cell parameters that can be applied to all kinds of circuit simulators [37]. In this approach, single-, double- and triple-diode PV models were achieved as a result of adjusting the diode equation at three different points (I_{sc} , V_{oc} & MPP). Relative errors of about 32% to 50% are obtained after testing the models. However, substantial improvement in the accuracy was observed upon further adjusting the equation at more than three points. Heterogeneous PV panel simulation is made possible using the proposed technique. Models validation was done

using the experimental data from the selected PV modules. It is concluded that single-diode PV models give the most accurate results with negligible relative error.

The parameters extraction of PV models (single-, double- and three-diode) were conducted using Coyote Optimization Algorithm (COA) [38] and whale optimisation algorithm (WOA) [39]. The COA is used because of its promising tracking and balance creation abilities coupled with its simplicity implementation simplicity due to its few control parameters requirements. Various investigations of the PV cells/modules were carried out through varying both environmental and physical conditions, followed by comprehensive statistical validation of the models. Whereas, the WOA-model was validated using MATLAB program simulation, while the optimisation technique was used to validate its effectiveness. At the same time, the simulation results were also compared with the experimental results of analysing the Kyocera KC200GT PV module [39]. The simulation and validation results obtained are in good agreement, showing that the proposed techniques are able to extract the models' parameters under different test conditions accurately. The models established are within the acceptable values of Root Mean Square Error (RMSE).

It is argued that there is no optimal PV model (either one- or two-diode) suitable for all the module types. This is because the modules are produced using different PV cell technologies; thus, they behave differently under any given physical and environmental conditions [40]. As such, the modelling accuracy depends on the module type used. However, a multidimensional diode PV model has been proposed in an attempt to fill the research gap [40]. In this method, diode network configuration for different types of cell technologies is utilised. This enables the simple extraction of the PV cell/module parameters. The simulation results are validated using the experimental data. A PV model suitable for all cell technologies is established. However, it is best performed for single- and double-diode models. Therefore, it serves as a bedrock for future advanced study.

2.5 Conclusion

Numerous factors like simplicity in simulation, complexity in mathematical modelling, processing speed, accuracy, recombination of carriers and so on are considered when choosing the type of PV cell to be used in PV modules/array modelling [22]. These led to different studies by authors using distinctive solar cell models for improved accuracy and efficiency. Several studies used MATLAB programming to model and simulate solar photovoltaic modules. However, the approaches used in most of the studies are too complicated, which require longer computation time and lower processing speed. Meanwhile, in the simplified approaches, most of the I-V equation parameters are either neglected or approximated, resulting in compromise with accuracy. Therefore, based on this review, the SDM shown in Fig. 2 was used in this study for the module implementation. The model has been proved to offer the best compromise between accuracy and simplicity [17]. The programming technique in the proposed method can be efficiently and effectively implemented in any circuit simulator based on the manufacturer's datasheet information, thereby enabling the realisation of the anticipated improvements against the traditional techniques.

Chapter 3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction

The techniques of PV modules modelling have been continuously modified and improved to find the best approach suitable for current and emerging modules. However, based on the reviewed literature in the preceding section, it was established that majority of the proposed modelling methods exhibit some level of approximations and estimations of the I-V equation parameters, which invariably affect the accuracy and suitability of the techniques. Most importantly, at operating conditions of high solar irradiance and temperature. Therefore, one notable gap, which when filled could improve the modelling accuracy, is the proposition of technique that will eliminate the guess of any of the I-V equation parameters by trial and error while the algorithm is being run. If not eliminated, then the accuracy of the algorithm may be affected due to variations in the properties of modules' materials. For ensuring authenticity of the modelling techniques, all parameters of the I-V equation need to be determined without assuming any constant values. Because it is impractical to introduce any constant values outside the given datasheet information, except for the globally accepted constants.

To address these challenges, an improved modelling technique suitable for the majority of the PV modules technologies utilising only the manufacturer's datasheet information and does not require any initial guess value(s) or finding the I-V equation parameters by trial and error is necessary. Therefore, the proposed PV modelling method presented in the subsequent sections of this chapter aims to address these challenges.

In this study, a five-parameter SDM PV module is modelled by adjusting the I-V equation parameters based on the manufacturer's datasheet information. Then an iterative algorithm technique employing Newton-Raphson iteration is used to implement the module using MATLAB programming in the MATLAB editor window. The performance of different PV module technologies implemented are evaluated at STC. Analyses of the I-V and P-V curves characteristics

of the developed models are carried out. Further analyses of the implemented models are conducted by varying the operating temperature and solar irradiance. Models validation is performed by comparing the results obtained with that of the selected in-built PV model using the manufacturer's datasheet. During the model validation, different factors affecting the performance of the module are evaluated. A Simulink version of the proposed modelling algorithm has been developed for easy to use with any type of circuit simulator. Finally, the developed model was used to simulate the traditional P&O MPPT algorithm in the MATLAB/Simulink environment.

3.2 Unknown Parameters Estimation

To model and analyse the non-linear output characteristics of the PV module, all parameters of equation (4) must be known. However, the PV module manufacturers provide some limited information in the datasheet, which necessitate estimating the unknown parameters from the given ones. In this research, the following five unknown parameters (I_L , I_{sat} , m , R_s & R_{sh}) were determined before the modelling process began.

3.2.1 Estimating the light-generated current (I_L)

The light-generated current can be obtained by rearranging equation (3) in terms of the m , I , I_{sat} , V_d , V_t , R_s & R_{sh} and making I_L subject of the relation. Therefore, arriving at equation (5).

$$I_L = I + I_{sat} \left[e^{\left(\frac{V_d + IR_s}{mV_t} \right)} - 1 \right] + \frac{(V_d + IR_s)}{R_{sh}} \quad (5)$$

The I_L is basically affected by solar irradiation and temperature; as such, the relationships can be represented in terms of the current/temperature coefficient, K_i [13, 16, 17, 20] based on the general assumptions that $I_L \approx I_{sc}$ at STC.

$$I_L = \frac{(Irr)}{Irr_{stc}} \cdot [I_{L,stc} + K_i(T - T_{stc})] \quad (6)$$

Where: K_i = current/temperature coefficient; Irr_{stc} = solar irradiation at STC

T = actual temperature in Kelvin ; T_{stc} = temperature at STC in Kelvin;

Irr = actual solar irradiation on the PV surface; $I_{L,stc}$ = light – generated current at STC

3.2.2 Estimating the reverse-saturation current (I_{sat})

For model simplification at STC, the R_s is considered to be very small, while the R_{sh} is infinitely large; thus, their effects are neglected [41, 42]. After ignoring the last part of equation (3) [41, 42], then the new I-V equation becomes:

$$I = I_L - I_{sat} \left[e^{\left(\frac{V_d + IR_s}{m \cdot V_t} \right)} - 1 \right] \quad (7)$$

Analysing the equation at three main points (short-circuit point, open-circuit point and maximum power point) of the I-V curve yields the following [16, 20].

i. Short-circuit point ($V = 0, I = I_{sc, stc}$)

$$I_{sc, stc} = I_{L, stc} - I_{sat, stc} \left[e^{\left(\frac{I_{sc, stc} \cdot R_s}{m V_t} \right)} - 1 \right] \quad (8)$$

ii. Open-circuit point ($V = V_{oc, stc}, I = 0$)

$$0 = I_{L, stc} - I_{sat, stc} \left[e^{\left(\frac{V_{oc, stc}}{m V_t} \right)} - 1 \right] \quad (9)$$

iii. Maximum power point ($V = V_{mp}, I = I_{mp}$)

$$I_{mp} = I_{L, stc} - I_{sat, stc} \left[e^{\left(\frac{V_{mp} + I_{mp} \cdot R_s}{m V_t} \right)} - 1 \right] \quad (10)$$

By approximations and simplifications, the reverse-saturation current (at STC) of equation (9) can be expressed as:

$$I_{sat, stc} = I_{sc, stc} \left[e^{\left(\frac{-V_{oc, stc}}{m V_t} \right)} \right] \quad (11)$$

Where: $V_{oc, stc}$ = open – circuit voltage at STC ; $I_{sc, stc}$ = short – circuit current at STC;

I_{mp} = current at MPP; V_{mp} = voltage at MPP; $I_{sat, stc}$ = reverse – saturation current at STC

The I_{sat} does not explicitly depend on the solar irradiation but on the temperature [13, 19, 20]. Thus, according to the derivation presented in [13, 15-17, 20], the I_{sat} equation is expressed as follows.

$$I_{sat} = I_{sat,stc} \cdot \left[\frac{T}{T_{stc}} \right]^3 e \left[\left(\frac{q \cdot V_{gap}}{m \cdot k} \right) \left(\frac{1}{T_{stc}} - \frac{1}{T} \right) \right] \quad (12)$$

Where: V_{gap} = Bandgap energy, which has values between 1.1 to 1.12 eV for Silicon materials and 1.35 eV for GaGs.

An improved formed of equation (12) has been proposed by [16], in which K_i and K_v are introduced to equation (11); this is to ensure best I-V curve fittings at various temperatures while minimising the model errors around the V_{oc} points.

3.2.3 Estimating the diode ideality factor (m)

The diode ideality factor, m was evaluated at STC using the manufacturer's datasheet information and the three-main points of the I-V curve; based on the general assumptions that $I_L \approx I_{sc}$ [15]. Thus, as described by [41], the m is found as follows.

$$m = \frac{K_v - \frac{V_{oc}}{T_{stc}}}{N_s \cdot V_{t,stc} \left(\frac{K_i}{I_{sc,stc}} - \frac{3}{T_{stc}} - \frac{V_{gap}}{k \cdot T_{stc}^2} \right)} \quad (13)$$

Where: K_v = voltage/temperature coefficient

3.2.4 Estimating the series and shunt resistances (R_s & R_{sh})

In most literature, the effect of shunt resistance is neglected, where only the series resistances are considered. However, in this study, both parameters are considered to be a pair $\{R_s, R_{sh}\}$ [17] and estimated simultaneously, as such one cannot be left at the expense of the other, unlike in some studies which consider them to be independent parameters. The pair estimation of these parameters will ensure a good fit for the models I-V curve and convergence between the maximum power points of the manufacturer's datasheet and the estimated parameters (i.e. $V_{mp,m} \cdot I_{mp,m} = V_{mp,e} \cdot I_{mp,e} = P_{max,m} = P_{max,e}$).

Where: $V_{mp,m}$ = manufacturer's V_{mp} ; $I_{mp,m}$ = manufacturer's I_{mp}

$V_{mp,e}$ = estimated V_{mp} ; $I_{mp,e}$ = estimated I_{mp} ; $P_{max,m}$ = manufacturer's P_{max} $P_{max,e}$ = estimated P_{max}

Therefore, based on the three main points of the I-V curve and deriving equation (3) at these points while applying the iterative solution approach presented in [15, 17, 20], the following equations are obtained.

$$I_{mp} = \frac{V_{mp}}{P_{mp}} \quad (14)$$

$$I_{mp} = I_{L,stc} - I_{sat,stc} \left[e^{\left(\frac{V_{mp} + I_{mp} \cdot R_s}{m \cdot V_t} \right)} - 1 \right] + \frac{(V_{mp} + I_{mp} \cdot R_s)}{R_{sh}} \quad (15)$$

By substitution and rearrangement, equation (15) becomes:

$$R_{sh} = \frac{(V_{mp} + I_{mp} \cdot R_s)}{I_{sc,stc} - I_{sc,stc} \left[e^{\left(\frac{V_{mp} + I_{mp} \cdot R_s - V_{oc,stc}}{mV_t} \right)} \right] + I_{sc,stc} \left[e^{\left(\frac{-V_{oc,stc}}{mV_t} \right)} \right]} \quad (16)$$

Further substitution and simplification give:

$$R_{sh} = \frac{V_{mp}(V_{mp} + I_{mp} \cdot R_s)}{\left\{ V_{mp} \cdot I_{mp} - V_{mp} \cdot I_{sat} e^{\left[\left(\frac{V_{mp} + I_{mp} \cdot R_s}{mV_t} \right)} \right] + V_{mp} \cdot I_{sat} - P_{max,m} \right\}} \quad (17)$$

From equations (16 & 17), it can be seen that for each value of R_s , there is a corresponding value of R_{sh} . Since the two parameters are evaluated as a pair and their initial values are unknown, this necessitates the introduction of an initial guess for these values before the commencement of the iterative solution process. In which R_s is assumed to be zero while R_{sh} initial value is found using equation (18).

$$R_{sh} = R_{sh,min} = \frac{V_{mp}}{I_{sc,stc} - I_{mp}} - \frac{V_{oc,stc} - V_{mp}}{I_{mp}} \quad (18)$$

Even though R_{sh} values remain unknown, but it is still greater than the $R_{sh,min}$ [16, 20] and the assumptions are said to be good. The R_{sh} is found from equation (17) by slowly incrementing the R_s values starting from zero. The iterative process continues until $P_{max,m} = P_{max,e}$. Finally, the estimated values of R_s and R_{sh} are obtained.

Indeed, the proposed modelling technique utilises some constant values, for example, the charge of an electron, the Boltzmann's constant and so on. However, it is noteworthy that these

constants are based on the general knowledge of the physical characteristics of semiconductor materials and do not in any way, affect the accuracy of the modelling results.

3.3 Proposed Algorithm

An iterative algorithm to model the PV module adjusted in the preceding section was also proposed. Considering the non-linear nature of the I-V equation, the Newton-Raphson technique was assumed to be the most suitable and thus used for the algorithm implementation. According to the equation (19) [20], the Newton-Raphson continues to operate using a single iteration loop until the set stopping points condition (i.e. either equations 19 or 20) are reached.

$$Y_{n+1} = Y_n - \frac{f(Y_n)}{f'(Y_n)} \quad (19)$$

Where: Y_{n+1} = next value of a function; Y_n = current value of a function

$f(Y_n)$ = actual function value; $f'(Y_n)$ = function derivatives;

The maximum tolerable error for the algorithm is found based on the following equation [20].

$$\text{Error} = \frac{|Z_{n+1} - Z_n|}{|Z_{n+1}|} \times 100 \quad (20)$$

An iterative algorithm flowchart used for the module parameters estimation and implementation is shown in Fig. 6, while the MATLAB m-files are presented in appendix A.

The algorithm was tested based on the data obtained from three PV manufacturing technologies. Tables 1 [43], 2 [44] and 3 [45] show parameters of the modules tested.

Table 1: Datasheet parameters for c-Si M2453BB PV module at STC

Parameter	Value	Unit
Short-circuit current, I_{sc}	8.70	Ampere (A)
Open-circuit voltage, V_{oc}	37.70	Voltage (V)
Current at Pmax, I_{mp}	8.20	Ampere (A)
Voltage at Pmax, V_{mp}	30.10	Voltage (V)
Maximum power, $P_{max,e}$	246.820000	Watts (W)
Temperature coefficient of open-circuit voltage V_{oc} , K_v	-0.32	%/°C
Temperature coefficient of short-circuit current I_{sc} , K_i	0.032	%/°C
The number of cells, n	60	-

Fig. 6: Iterative algorithm flowchart

Table 2: Datasheet parameters for c-Si CHSM6610P-220 PV module at STC

Parameter	Value	Unit
Short-circuit current, I_{sc}	8.46	Ampere (A)
Open-circuit voltage, V_{oc}	36.92	Voltage (V)
Current at Pmax, I_{mp}	7.86	Ampere (A)
Voltage at Pmax, V_{mp}	28.02	Voltage (V)
Maximum power, $P_{max,e}$	220.237200	Watts (W)
Temperature coefficient of open-circuit voltage V_{oc} , K_v	-0.344	%/°C
Temperature coefficient of short-circuit current I_{sc} , K_i	0.052	%/°C
The number of cells, n	60	-

3.4 Model Validation

Model validation of the developed algorithm was performed by analysing the performance characteristics of the Solarex MSX60 module [45] at different conditions of temperature and

solar irradiation. The modules plotted I-V and P-V curves are compared with the results obtained in [16, 45].

Table 3: Datasheet parameters for Solarex MSX60 PV module at STC

Parameter	Value	Unit
Short-circuit current, I_{sc}	3.80	Ampere (A)
Open-circuit voltage, V_{oc}	21.10	Voltage (V)
Current at Pmax, I_{mp}	3.50	Ampere (A)
Voltage at Pmax, V_{mp}	17.10	Voltage (V)
Maximum power, $P_{max,e}$	59.850000	Watts (W)
Temperature coefficient of open-circuit voltage V_{oc} , K_v	-80.0	mV/°C
Temperature coefficient of short-circuit current I_{sc} , K_i	2.4	mA/°C
The number of cells, n	36	-

3.5 Simulink Model

The proposed circuit simulation approach presented in [17] has been used to simulate the PV module implemented in this study, based on the equivalent circuit of SDM shown in Fig. 2. The design was made in such a way that it can work with any type of circuit simulator. A computational block having the input parameters m , V , I , I_{sat} & I_L computes the model current source (I_m) in which R_s & R_{sh} regulate the model output accordingly. The Simulink block diagram of the model is shown in Fig. 7, while the detailed model subsystem blocks are shown in appendix B.

Fig. 7: Simulink version of the proposed module

3.6 Conclusion

A five-parameter SDM PV module was modelled through the I-V equation parameters estimation based on the manufacturer's datasheet information. An iterative algorithm technique was then used to implement the module using MATLAB programming in the MATLAB editor window. The performance of different PV module technologies implemented was evaluated at STC. Analyses of the I-V and P-V curves characteristics of the developed models were carried out. Further analyses of the implemented models were conducted by varying the operating temperature and solar irradiance. Models validation was performed by comparing the results obtained with that of the selected in-built PV model using the manufacturer's datasheet. During the model validation, different factors affecting the performance of the module are evaluated. The Simulink version of the proposed algorithm was also developed for easy to use with any circuit simulator. Finally, the developed model was used to simulate traditional P&O MPPT algorithms in the MATLAB/Simulink environment.

The algorithm was simultaneously implemented in MATLAB_R2020a version running on both a MacBook Pro with a MacOS Big Sur version 11.0.1, 2.7 GHz Dual-Core Intel Core i5 and 8GB memory of RAM; as well as a Lenovo Laptop PC with a Windows 10 Home Edition, 2.11 GHz Intel Core i5-10210U CPU, 8GB memory of RAM and 64-bit Operating System respectively.

Chapter 4. RESULTS ANALYSES AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 Introduction

In this chapter, the module modelling results implemented in the previous section are first presented, analysed and discussed. This is followed by the I-V and P-V curves characteristics results of the developed models. The performance results of different PV module technologies implemented and evaluated at STC are shown. After which, the model validation results of the selected PV panel using the iterative algorithm while varying the test conditions are discussed. Finally, a short conclusion based on the results is drawn.

4.2 PV module modelling results

The module parameters adjustment results for the three PV manufacturing technologies tested in section 3.3 are presented here.

Table 4: Adjusted parameters for c-Si M2453BB PV module at STC

Parameter	Value	Unit
Short-circuit current, I_{sc}	8.70	Ampere (A)
Open-circuit voltage, V_{oc}	37.70	Voltage (V)
Current at MPP, I_{mp}	8.20	Ampere (A)
Voltage at MPP, V_{mp}	30.10	Voltage (V)
Temperature coefficient of open-circuit voltage, K_v	-0.1206	%/K
Temperature coefficient of short-circuit current, K_i	0.0028	%/K
The number of cells, n	60	-
Maximum experimental power, $P_{max,e}$	246.820000	Watts (W)
Maximum modelled power, $P_{max,m}$	246.819620	Watts (W)
Diode ideality factor, m	1.020626	-
Light-generated current, I_L	8.703960	Ampere (A)
Reverse saturation current, I_{sat}	3.39612e-10	Ampere (A)
Series resistance, R_s	0.366000	Ohm (Ω)
Shunt resistance, R_{sh}	861.453296	Ohm (Ω)

It can be seen from Tables 4, 5 & 6 that the implemented model correctly matched with the experimental data obtained by the manufacturers at STC based on the analysed parameters.

Table 5: Adjusted parameters for c-Si CHSM6610P-220 PV module at STC

Parameter	Value	Unit
Short-circuit current, I_{sc}	8.46	Ampere (A)
Open-circuit voltage, V_{oc}	36.92	Voltage (V)
Current at MPP, I_{mp}	7.86	Ampere (A)
Voltage at MPP, V_{mp}	28.02	Voltage (V)
Temperature coefficient of open-circuit voltage, K_v	-0.1270	%/K
Temperature coefficient of short-circuit current, K_i	0.0044	%/K
The number of cells, n	60	-
Maximum experimental power, $P_{max,e}$	220.237200	Watts (W)
Maximum modelled power, $P_{max,m}$	220.237031	Watts (W)
Diode ideality factor, m	1.041447	-
Light-generated current, I_L	8.473546	Ampere (A)
Reverse saturation current, I_{sat}	8.51763e-10	Ampere (A)
Series resistance, R_s	0.567000	Ohm (Ω)
Shunt resistance, R_{sh}	366.391745	Ohm (Ω)

Table 6: Adjusted parameters for Solarex MSX60 PV module at STC

Parameter	Value	Unit
Short-circuit current, I_{sc}	3.80	Ampere (A)
Open-circuit voltage, V_{oc}	21.10	Voltage (V)
Current at MPP, I_{mp}	3.50	Ampere (A)
Voltage at MPP, V_{mp}	17.10	Voltage (V)
Temperature coefficient of open-circuit voltage, K_v	-0.08	V/ $^{\circ}$ C
Temperature coefficient of short-circuit current, K_i	0.0024	A/ $^{\circ}$ C
The number of cells, n	60	-
Maximum experimental power, $P_{max,e}$	59.850000	Watts (W)
Maximum modelled power, $P_{max,m}$	59.849726	Watts (W)
Diode ideality factor, m	1.044288	-
Light-generated current, I_L	3.808285	Ampere (A)
Reverse saturation current, I_{sat}	1.19287e-09	Ampere (A)
Series resistance, R_s	0.316000	Ohm (Ω)
Shunt resistance, R_{sh}	145.352886	Ohm (Ω)

A comparison of the values of *diode ideality factor* (m) for these tested modules has also been made and presented in Table 7. It can be observed that the values differ from one another, although all the modules are from the same family group (i.e. c-Si). This further highlighted the

inadequacies of the previous modelling methods that used an assumed constant value of m . Thus, the values need to be calculated for each module separately for an accurate determination of the I-V curve.

Table 7: Diode ideality factor comparisons for the tested modules

Module Type	Number of cells (n)	Diode ideality factor (m)
c-Si M2453BB	60	1.020626
c-Si CHSM6610P-220	60	1.041447
c-Si MSX60	36	1.044288

Table 8: Power error comparisons for the tested modules

Module Type	Actual Power (W)	Modelled Power (W)	Power Error (Δ)
c-Si M2453BB	246.820000	246.819620	-0.000380
c-Si CHSM6610P-220	220.237200	220.237031	-0.000169
c-Si MSX60	59.850000	59.849726	-0.000274

Similarly, Table 8 shows the comparison between the actual and modelled power output of the modules as computed by the algorithm. The error measurement was done to ascertain the algorithm's precision based on the tested datasets. It can be deduced from the table that the modelling algorithm yielded accurate results as expected, with c-Si CHSM6610P-220 having the best-matched values due to the least power error measurement.

4.3 I-V and P-V characteristics results

The I-V and P-V curve characteristics of the modules were also analysed. The results are shown in Figs. 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, & 13 respectively. The solid blue lines on the graphs indicated the experimental output, while the dashed red lines represented the adjusted parameters output.

As observed from the figures, the I-V and P-V curves of the adjusted and experimental data based on the manufacturer's datasheet successfully coincide at the curves' three-main points for all tested modules. Thus, the primary objective of the proposed modelling technique has been achieved.

I-V curves of the c-Si M2453BB module at STC & adjusted parameters

Fig. 8: Compared I-V curves for the c-Si M2453BB module

P-V curves of the c-Si M2453BB module at STC & adjusted parameters

Fig. 9: Compared P-V curves for the c-Si M2453BB module

I-V curves of the c-Si CHSM6610P-220 module at STC & adjusted parameters

Fig. 10: Compared I-V curves for the c-Si CHSM6610P-220 module

P-V curves of the c-Si CHSM6610P-220 module at STC & adjusted parameters

Fig. 11: Compared P-V curves for the c-Si CHSM6610P-220 module

Fig. 12: Compared I-V curves for the Solarex MSX60 module

Fig. 13: Compared P-V curves for the Solarex MSX60 module

4.4 Model validation results

In this section, the I-V and P-V characteristics results of the developed models tested based on the manufacturer's datasheet values for some selected solar panels to verify their agreement over the range of temperature and insolation values are presented.

(a) Diagram of the I-V curve characteristics

(b) Diagram of the P-V curve characteristics

Fig. 14: Validation of Solarex MSX60 model at varying irradiance

The I-V and P-V curves characteristics results for the Solarex MSX60 module at different irradiance and temperature are shown in Figs. 14 & 15 respectively. The results obtained clearly show an improvement of the results obtained in [16, 45] using the same PV module but with a different modelling approach. Thus, validate the proposed modelling technique performance at conditions different from the STC.

(c) Diagram of the I-V curve characteristics

(d) Diagram of the P-V curve characteristics

Fig. 15: Validation of Solarex MSX60 model at varying temperature

4.5 Simulink model results

In addition, the Simulink circuit model results for the Solarex MSX60 module tested in section 3.5 are shown in Figures 16 & 17.

Fig. 16: I-V curve for Simulink model of Solarex MSX60

Fig. 17: P-V curve for Simulink model of Solarex MSX60

It can be deduced from the figures that the I-V and P-V results of the Simulink model were found to be the same as the ones obtained in section 4.3 for the Solarex MSX60 module. Therefore, the proposed modelling technique has proved to be efficient and consistent in both the MATLAB m-file and the Simulink maths block functions.

4.6 Conclusion

Results presentation, analyses and discussion were made in the previous sections of this chapter (section 4.2 – 4.5). These include the estimation and model of the parameter implementation using both m-file and the Simulink math block functions; models' validation at different conditions from the STC; I-V and P-V curves characteristics evaluation, amongst others. The effects of using constant values of the I-V equation parameters were also evaluated.

It was concluded that the proposed modelling technique have shown good agreement between the experimental and modelled results with good precision and improved the previous modelling results obtained by some authors. Therefore, it can be regarded as a flexible, more robust, and simpler PV module modelling approach, which can fit into many SPS design requirements and serves as a promising alternative to the Simulink in-built models.

Chapter 5. CONCLUSIONS

5.1 Introduction

In this research, a soft modelling method for the PV modules has been proposed, implemented and analysed. MATLAB m-file script and Simulink environment were used for the algorithm implementation and analyses. The primary aim of matching the experimental and the model output curves of PV modules was achieved. The proposed algorithm in this study was adopted from the research of [13, 17], which were modified and improved to accommodate all the I-V equation parameters necessary for accurate PV module modelling. The use of arbitrary values of some parameters was eliminated, which consequently improved the accuracy of other module parameters estimation and overall I-V and P-V characteristics.

5.2 Lessons Learned

The learning outcomes of this study include but not limited to the following:

1. Comprehensive understanding of the working principles and parameters' composition of single- and double-diode PV cell/module/array models, respectively.
2. Derivation and solution of SDM equivalent-circuit parameters of the selected panels using MATLAB programming in MATLAB/Simulink.
3. Understanding the effects of changes in temperature and solar irradiance on the PV module parameters.
4. The effects of assuming some constant values on the accuracy of the PV module modelling techniques were also learned.
5. The I-V & P-V curve characteristics comparative analyses between the proposed model and selected solar panels using the manufacturer's datasheet values to verify their agreement over a range of insolation and temperature values.

5.3 Contributions to Knowledge

The proposed algorithm uses the manufacturer's datasheet information to implement a five-parameter SDM PV module. As highlighted in various studies, most of the proposed modelling approaches used an arbitrary value of the *diode ideality constant* (m) [15], which consequently affects the accuracy of the other module parameters estimation. The effect is more prominent in methods that employ *iterative techniques* (due to sensitivity of the initial guess values) in determining these unknown parameters, leading to *convergence* problems.

Similarly, the shunt resistance (R_{sh}) is assumed to be very high or infinite and hence neglected in some approaches. However, this type of assumption leads to a large error in the algorithm implementation, especially at very high temperature and irradiance conditions.

Therefore, in this proposed algorithm, all the five unknown parameters (m , I_L , I_o , R_s & R_{sh}) of the SDM are evaluated without assuming an arbitrary constant value of the diode ideality factor while computing the R_s and R_{sh} simultaneously. Three main points of the I-V curve (*short-circuit, open-circuit and maximum power*) together with the datasheet information are used in the simplifications and approximations, leading to the resulted equations.

The initial guess values of R_s and R_{sh} were used, with an assumption that at standard test condition (STC), $I_{L_stc} \gg I_{sat_stc} \left[e \left(\frac{IR_{sh}}{mN_sV_t} \right) - 1 \right]$.

5.4 Conclusion

The algorithm proposed meets the key features of minimal or negligible differences between the *modelled and actual measurements data*, most especially at the maximum power points, while exhibiting a *fast convergence*. It also proved to have improved the results obtained in previous studies, which employed a similar approach but with many initial guess values.

5.5 Suggestions for Future Work

1. For the sake of simplicity, a SDM PV module was used in this study. In future research, a DDM can be used to advance the current technique. However, this may require advanced and complicated modelling and simulation procedures.

2. Validation of the proposed modelling technique using real-outdoor experimental data is beyond the scope of the current study. It is suggested that this should be part of a future study's objectives.
3. Finally, future studies should also include additional error measurements to further improve the algorithm's precision and accuracy.

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX A. MATLAB SCRIPT FILE

A.1 PV Modelling Algorithm for Solarex MSX60 (Parameters Estimation)

This section shows the modelling algorithm used for the parameters' estimation and model implementation. An algorithm for Solarex MSX60 is presented here for illustration. All other modules implemented in this study followed the same format.

```
% An Improved (five-parameter) PV module modelling algorithm

clear variables
clc
close all hidden

%% Manufacturer's Datasheet Information for the Solarex MSX60 PV module

Isc_stc = 3.8;           % STC value of short-circuit current (A)
Voc_stc = 21.1;        % STC value of open-circuit voltage (V)
Imp = 3.5;             % Module current at MPP (A)
Vmp = 17.1;           % Module voltage at MPP (V)
MP_e = Vmp*Imp;       % Experimental maximum power output of the module (W)
Kv = -0.08;           % Voltage/temperature coefficient (V/degC)
Ki = 0.0024;          % Current/temperature coefficient (A/degC)
Ns = 36;              % Series-connected cells
Np = 1;               % Parallel-connected cells

%% Constant values

k = 1.3806503e-23;    % Boltzmann's constant (J/K)
q = 1.60217646e-19;  % Electron charge (C)
Vgap = 1.8e-19;       % Chosen arbitrary constant value of the energy bandgap for crystalline silicon (1.12 eV)

%% Standard Test Condition (STC)

Irr_stc = 1000;       % Irradiance at STC (W/m^2)
T_stc = 25 + 273.15; % Operating temperature at STC (K)
Am = 1.5;             % Air mass

%% Model adjustment relations at STC

T = T_stc;           % Temperature for evaluating the model after the parameter extraction
Irr = Irr_stc;       % Irradiance for evaluating the model after the parameter extraction
DT = T-T_stc;        % Change in temperature

Vt_stc = k * T_stc / q; % Equation to compute the thermal voltage at STC
Vt = k * T / q;       % Equation to compute the thermal voltage at adjusted temperature

Isc = (Isc_stc + Ki*DT) *Irr/Irr_stc; % Actual short-circuit current at adjusted conditions

%% An equation to compute the diode ideality factor
```

```

m = (Kv - Voc_stc/T_stc)/(Ns * Vt_stc * (Ki/Isc_stc - 3/T_stc - Vgap/(k *
T_stc^2)));

%% Parameters specification for the algorithm

Rs_inc = 0.001;           % Series resistnace (Rs) increment

Max_tol_error = 0.0001;  % Maximum tolerable power error

nv = 100;                % Number of voltage points in each iteration

nimax = 500000;         % Maximum number of iterations for each value of 'm'

plott = 0;              % Disable Plot function during loop execution is used

%% Assumptions and setting of initial parameters

% At the maximum power conditions, the minimum value of Shunt (Rsh) re-
sistance is used to enable their initial guess:

Rsh_min = Vmp/(Isc_stc-Imp) - (Voc_stc - Vmp)/ Imp;

% Initial guesses for the Series (Rs) and Shunt (Rsh) resistances are:
Rs = 0;
Rsh = Rsh_min;

%% Iterative loop execution until the Experimental Maximum Power of the
module at STC (MP,e,experimental)
% is equivalent to the Maximum Power of the model (MP,model)

P_error = Inf;          % dummy value (error in the power calculation bewtween
MP,e & MP,m)
ni = 0;                % counter

while (P_error>Max_tol_error) && (Rsh > 0) && (ni < nimax)

ni = ni + 1;

Il_stc = (Rs+Rsh)/Rsh * Isc_stc;          % Light-generated current values
at STC
Il = (Il_stc + Ki*DT) *Irr/Irr_stc;      % Actual light-generated current
of the module

Isat = (Il - Voc_stc/Rsh)/(exp(Voc_stc/Vt/m/Ns)-1); % Reverse saturation
current values at STC
% Since at I=Isc and Voc=0, the following relation holds (Isat_stc = Isat),
% then the equation gives the reverse saturation current at any conditions

Rs = Rs + Rs_inc; % Increments of the Rs for fast convergence and estima-
tion of the actual Rs & Rsh
Rsh_ = Rsh;

Rsh = Vmp*(Vmp+Imp*Rs) / (Vmp*Il-Vmp*Isat*exp((Vmp+Imp*Rs)/Vt/Ns/m)+Vmp*Isat-
MP_e);

% The equation above computes the actual shunt resistance of the module

%% I-V equation solution

% Solving the I-V equation for several (Voltage, Current) pairs using
% Newton-Raphson

clear V
clear I

```

```

V = 0:Voc_stc/nv:Voc_stc;          % Voltage vector
I = zeros(1,size(V,2));          % Current vector

for j = 1 : size(V,2)

% Solves  $g = I - f(I,V) = 0$  with Newton-Raphson

g(j) = I1-Isat*(exp((V(j)+I(j)*Rs)/Vt/Ns/m)-1)-(V(j)+I(j)*Rs)/Rsh-I(j);

while (abs(g(j)) > 0.001)

g(j) = I1-Isat*(exp((V(j)+I(j)*Rs)/Vt/Ns/m)-1)-(V(j)+I(j)*Rs)/Rsh-I(j);
glin(j) = -Isat*Rs/Vt/Ns/m*exp((V(j)+I(j)*Rs)/Vt/Ns/m)-Rs/Rsh-1;
I_(j) = I(j) - g(j)/glin(j);
I(j) = I_(j);

end

end % for j = 1 : size(V,2)

% Power calculation from the I-V equation at the adjusted conditions
P = (Np*I1-Isat*(exp((V+I.*Rs)/Vt/Ns/m)-1)-(V+I.*Rs)/Rsh).*V;

Pmax_m = max(P);                  % Maximum power of the Modelled module at the
adjusted condition

P_error = (Pmax_m-MP_e);          % Error in the maximum power measurements of
the module (between the adjusted model & the experimental)

end

if (Rsh<0); Rsh = Rsh_;
end

Vgap_ = -(k * T_stc^2) * (((Kv - Voc_stc/T_stc)/(m * Ns * Vt_stc)) -
(Ki/I1_stc) + 3/T_stc);

%% Output Graphs of the Experimental and Model measurements (I-V & P-V
curves)

% A graph of Current vs Voltage at STC
figure(1)
grid on
hold on
xlabel(['Voltage (V)', newline, '\bf I-V curve of the Solarex MSX60 mod-
ule at STC'],'FontName','Times');
ylabel('Current (A)','FontName','Times');
xlim([0 Voc_stc*1.08]);
ylim([0 Isc_stc*1.08]);
plot(V,I,'LineWidth',2,'Color','b')
plot([0 Vmp Voc_stc],[Isc_stc Imp 0],'*','LineWidth',2,'Mark-
erSize',4,'Color','b')
ax=gca; ax.FontSize=12;

% A graph of the Current vs Voltage at the adjusted condition
figure(2)
grid on
hold on
xlabel(['Voltage (V)', newline, '\bf I-V curve of the Solarex MSX60 module
at adjusted paramters'],'FontName','Times');
ylabel('Current (A)','FontName','Times');
xlim([0 max(V)*1.08]);
ylim([0 max(I)*1.08]);
plot(V,I,'LineWidth',2,'Color','r')
plot([0 Vmp Voc_stc],[Isc_stc Imp 0],'o','LineWidth',2,'Mark-
erSize',4,'Color','r')
ax=gca; ax.FontSize=12;

% A graph of the Power vs Voltage at STC
figure(3)

```

```

grid on
hold on
xlabel(['Voltage (V)', newline, '\bf P-V curve of the Solarex MSX60 mod-
ule at STC'],'FontName','Times');
ylabel('Power (W)','FontName','Times');
xlim([0 Voc_stc*1.08])
ylim([0 Vmp*Imp*1.08]);
plot(V,P,'LineWidth',2,'Color','b')
plot([0 Vmp Voc_stc],[0 Vmp*Imp 0],'*','LineWidth',2,'MarkerSize',4,'Col-
or','b')
ax=gca; ax.FontSize=12;

% A graph of the Power vs Voltage at the adjusted condition
figure(4)
grid on
hold on
xlabel(['Voltage (V)', newline, '\bf P-V curve of the Solarex MSX60 module
at adjusted parameters'],'FontName','Times');
ylabel('Power (W)','FontName','Times');
xlim([0 Voc_stc*1.08]);
ylim([0 Vmp*Imp*1.08]);
plot(V,P,'LineWidth',2,'Color','r')
plot(V,P,[0 Vmp Voc_stc ],[0 MP_e 0 ],'o','LineWidth',2,'Mark-
erSize',4,'Color','r')
ax=gca; ax.FontSize=12;

% Module Adjusted Parameters

fprintf('Irr_stc = %f\n',Irr);
fprintf('T_stc = %f\n',T-273.15);
fprintf('Isc_stc = %f\n',Isc);
fprintf('Voc_stc = %f\n',Voc_stc);
fprintf('Imp = %f\n',Imp);
fprintf('Vmp = %f\n',Vmp);
fprintf('m = %f\n',m);
fprintf('Il = %f\n',Il);
fprintf('Isat = %g\n',Isat);
fprintf('Rs = %f\n',Rs);
fprintf('Rsh = %f\n',Rsh);
fprintf('Pmax,e = %f (Module maximum power at STC)\n',MP_e);
fprintf('Pmax,m = %f (Module maximum power at adjusted parame-
ters)\n',Pmax_m);
fprintf('Tolerable power error = %f\n',Max_tol_error);
fprintf('Power error recorded = %f\n',P_error);
fprintf('\n\n\n');

```

A.2 PV Modelling Algorithm for Solarex MSX60 (I-V & P-V Curves Comparisons)

This section shows the modelling algorithm used for the module implementation and the characteristics curves comparisons. An algorithm for Solarex MSX60 is presented here for illustration. All other modules implemented in this study followed the same format.

```
%% An Improved (five-parameter) PV module modelling algorithm

clear variables
clc
close all hidden

%% Manufacturer's Datasheet Information for the Solarex MSX60 PV module

Isc_stc = 3.8;           % STC value of short-circuit current (A)
Voc_stc = 21.1;        % STC value of open-circuit voltage (V)
Imp = 3.5;             % Module current at MPP (A)
Vmp = 17.1;           % Module voltage at MPP (V)
MP_e = Vmp*Imp;       % Experimental maximum power output of the module
(W)
Kv = -0.08;           % Voltage/temperature coefficient (V/K)
Ki = 0.0024;         % Current/temperature coefficient (A/K)
Ns = 36;              % Series-connected cells
Np = 1;               % Parallel-connected cells

%% Constant values

k = 1.3806503e-23;    % Boltzmann's constant (J/K)
q = 1.60217646e-19;  % Electron charge (C)
Vgap = 1.8e-19;       % Chosen arbitrary constant value of the energy
bandgap for crystalline silicon (1.12 eV)

%% Standard Test Condition (STC)

Irr_stc = 1000;       % Irradiance at STC (W/m^2)
T_stc = 25 + 273.15; % Operating temperature at STC (K)
Am = 1.5;             % Air mass

%% Model adjustment relations at STC

T = T_stc;           % Temperature for evaluating the model after the
                    % parameter extraction
Irr = Irr_stc;       % Irradiance for evaluating the model after the
                    % parameter extraction
DT = T-T_stc;       % Change in temperature

Vt_stc = k * T_stc / q; % Equation to compute the thermal voltage at STC
Vt = k * T / q;      % Equation to compute the thermal voltage at
                    % adjusted temperature

Isc = (Isc_stc + Ki*DT) *Irr/Irr_stc; % Actual short-circuit current at
adjusted conditions

%% An equation to compute the diode ideality factor

m = (Kv - Voc_stc/T_stc)/(Ns * Vt_stc * (Ki/Isc_stc - 3/T_stc - Vgap/(k *
T_stc^2)));

%% Parameters specification for the algorithm

Rs_inc = 0.001;      % Series resistnace (Rs) increment

Max_tol_error = 0.0001; % Maximum tolerable power error
```

```

nv = 100; % Number of voltage points in each iteration
nimax = 500000; % Maximum number of iterations for each value of 'm'
plott = 0; % Disable Plot function during loop execution is used

%% Assumptions and setting of initial parameters

% At the maximum power conditions, the minimum value of Shunt (Rsh) resistance
is used to enable their initial guess:

Rsh_min = Vmp/(Isc_stc-Imp) - (Voc_stc - Vmp)/ Imp;

% Initial guesses for the Series (Rs) and Shunt (Rsh) resistances are:
Rs = 0;
Rsh = Rsh_min;

% Iterative loop execution until the Experimental Maximum Power of the module
at STC (MP,experimental)is equivalent to the Maximum Power of the model
(MP,model)

P_error = Inf; % dummy value (error in the power calculation between
MP,e & MP,m)
ni = 0; % counter

while (P_error>Max_tol_error) && (Rsh > 0) && (ni < nimax)

ni = ni + 1;

Il_stc = (Rs+Rsh)/Rsh * Isc_stc; % Light-generated current values at STC
Il = (Il_stc + Ki*DT) *Irr/Irr_stc; % Actual light-generated current of the
module

Isat = (Il - Voc_stc/Rsh)/(exp(Voc_stc/Vt/m/Ns)-1); % Reverse saturation cur-
rent values at STC
% Since at I=Isc and Voc=0, the following relation holds (Isat_stc = Isat),
% then the equation gives the reverse saturation current at any conditions

Rs = Rs + Rs_inc; % Increments of the Rs for fast convergence and estimation
of the actual Rs & Rsh
Rsh_ = Rsh;

Rsh = Vmp*(Vmp+Imp*Rs)/(Vmp*Il-Vmp*Isat*exp((Vmp+Imp*Rs)/Vt/Ns/m)+Vmp*Isat-
MP_e);

% The equation above computes the actual shunt resistance of the module

%% I-V equation solution

% Solving the I-V equation for several (Voltage, Current) pairs using
% Newton-Raphson

clear V
clear I

V = 0:Voc_stc/nv:Voc_stc; % Voltage vector
I = zeros(1,size(V,2)); % Current vector

for j = 1 : size(V,2)

% Solves g = I - f(I,V) = 0 with Newton-Raphson

g(j) = Il-Isat*(exp((V(j)+I(j)*Rs)/Vt/Ns/m)-1)-(V(j)+I(j)*Rs)/Rsh-I(j);

while (abs(g(j)) > 0.001)

```

```

g(j) = Il-Isat*(exp((V(j)+I(j)*Rs)/Vt/Ns/m)-1)-(V(j)+I(j)*Rs)/Rsh-I(j);
glin(j) = -Isat*Rs/Vt/Ns/m*exp((V(j)+I(j)*Rs)/Vt/Ns/m)-Rs/Rsh-1;
I_(j) = I(j) - g(j)/glin(j);
I(j) = I_(j);

end
end % for j = 1 : size(V,2)

% Power calculation from the I-V equation at the adjusted conditions
P = (Np*Il-Isat*(exp((V+I.*Rs)/Vt/Ns/m)-1)-(V+I.*Rs)/Rsh).*V;

% Maximum power of the Modelled module at the adjusted condition
Pmax_m = max(P);

P_error = (Pmax_m-MP_e);
% Error in the maximum power measurements of the module (between the adjusted
model & the experimental)

end

if (Rsh<0); Rsh = Rsh_;
end

Vgap_ = -(k * T_stc^2) * (((Kv - Voc_stc/T_stc)/(m * Ns * Vt_stc)) - (Ki/Il_stc)
+ 3/T_stc);

%% Output Graphs of the Experimental and Model measurements (I-V & P-V curves)

% A graph of Current vs Voltage at STC & adjusted conditions
figure(5)
grid on
hold on
xlabel(['Voltage (V)', newline, '\bf I-V curves of the Solarex MSX60 module
at STC & adjusted parameters'],'FontName','Times');
ylabel('Current (A)','FontName','Times');
xlim([0 Voc_stc*1.08]);
ylim([0 Isc_stc*1.08]);
plot(V,I,'-','LineWidth',0.5,'Color','b') % solid blue line indicates STC
plot([0 Vmp Voc_stc],[Isc_stc Imp 0],'.','LineWidth',1,'Color','b')
xlim([0 max(V)*1.08]);
ylim([0 max(I)*1.08]);
plot(V,I,'--','LineWidth',2,'Color','r') % dashed red line indicates ad-
justed parameters
plot([0 Vmp Voc_stc ],[Isc_stc Imp 0 ],'o','LineWidth',0.5,'Mark-
erSize',6,'Color','r')
hold off
ax=gca; ax.FontSize=12;
text(0,Isc_stc,'Short-circuit point','VerticalAlignment','bottom','Font-
Size',11,'Color','k','FontName','Times');
text(Voc_stc,0,'Open-circuit point','HorizontalAlignment','right','Verti-
calAlignment','bottom','FontSize',11,'Color','k','FontName','Times');
text(Vmp,Imp,' \leftarrow Maximum Power Point','FontSize',11,'Color',
'k','FontName','Times');

% A graph of the Power vs Voltage at STC & adjusted conditions
figure(6)
grid on
hold on
xlabel(['Voltage (V)', newline, '\bf P-V curves of the Solarex MSX60 module
at STC & adjusted parameters'],'FontName','Times');
ylabel('Power (W)','FontName','Times');
xlim([0 Voc_stc*1.08])
ylim([0 Vmp*Imp*1.08]);
plot(V,P,'-','LineWidth',0.5,'Color','b') % solid blue line indicates STC
plot([0 Vmp Voc_stc],[0 Vmp*Imp 0],'.','LineWidth',2,'MarkerSize',1,'Col-
or','b')
plot(V,P,'--','LineWidth',2,'Color','r') % dashed red line indicates ad-
justed parameters
plot([0 Vmp Voc_stc ],[0 MP_e 0 ],'o','LineWidth',0.5,'MarkerSize',6,'Col-
or','r')

```

```

    text(Vmp,MP_e,' \leftarrow Maximum Power Point','FontSize',11,'Color',
'k','FontName','Times');
    hold off
    ax=gca; ax.FontSize=12;

    %% Module Adjusted Parameters

    fprintf('Irr_stc = %f\n',Irr);
    fprintf('T_stc   = %f\n',T-273.15);
    fprintf('Isc_stc = %f\n',Isc);
    fprintf('Voc_stc = %f\n',Voc_stc);
    fprintf('Imp     = %f\n',Imp);
    fprintf('Vmp     = %f\n',Vmp);
    fprintf('m       = %f\n',m);
    fprintf('Il      = %f\n',Il);
    fprintf('Isat    = %g\n',Isat);
    fprintf('Rs      = %f\n',Rs);
    fprintf('Rsh     = %f\n',Rsh);
    fprintf('Pmax,e   = %f (Module maximum power at STC)\n',MP_e);
    fprintf('Pmax,m   = %f (Module maximum power at adjusted parame-
ters)\n',Pmax_m);
    fprintf('Tolerable power error = %f\n',Max_tol_error);
    fprintf('Power error recorded = %f\n',P_error);
    fprintf('\n\n\n');

```

APPENDIX B. SIMULINK MODEL

This section shows the Simulink model used for the module parameters extraction and implementation and the characteristics curves comparisons.

An m-file for the **MSX60_Specification.m** used as the PV Simulink model PV input is presented here.

```
% An Improved (five-parameter) PV module modelling algorithm

clear variables
clc
close all hidden

%% Manufacturer's Datasheet Information for the c-Si MSX60 PV module

Iscn = 3.8;           % STC value of short-circuit current (A)
Vocn = 21.1;         % STC value of open-circuit voltage (V)
Imp = 3.5;           % Module current at MPP (Imp/A)
Vmp = 17.1;          % Module voltage at MPP (Vmp/V)
Pmax = Vmp*Imp;      % Experimental maximum power output of the module
                    % (Pmax/W)
Kv = -0.08;          % Voltage/temperature coefficient (%/C)
Ki = +0.0024;        % Current/temperature coefficient (%/C)
Ns = 36;             % Series-connected cells
Np = 1;              % Parallel-connected cells
Npp=1;               % Number of parallel-connected panels
Nss=1;               % number of series-connected panels

%% Constant values

k = 1.3806503e-23;   % Boltzmann's constant (J/K)
q = 1.60217646e-19; % Electron charge (C)
Vgap = 1.8e-19;      % Chosen arbitrary constant value of the energy
                    % bandgap for crystalline silicon (1.12 eV)

%% Standard Test Condition (STC)

Gn = 1000;           % Irradiance at STC (W/m^2)
Tn = 25 + 273.15;   % Operating temperature at STC (K)
Am = 1.5;            % Air mass

%% Model adjustment relations at STC

T = Tn;              % Temperature for evaluating the model after the
                    % parameter extraction
G = Gn;              % Irradiance for evaluating the model after the pa-
                    % rameter extraction
dT = T-Tn;           % Change in temperature
Io = Iscn;           % Light-generated current values at STC

Vtn = k*Tn/q;        % Equation to compute the thermal voltage at STC
Vt = k*T/q;          % Equation to compute the thermal voltage at ad-
                    % justed temperature

%% Calculated parameters

Ipvn = 3.808285; Rs = 0.316000; Rp = 145.352886;
```

A Simulink model for Solarex MSX60 PV module is shown here for illustration. All other modules implemented in this study followed the same format.

Figure 1: Simulink model of Solarex MSX60 PV module